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Impact Factor: 3.43

Cite this paper as : *Padma Yallapragada (2017), "A STUDY ON CONSUMER BUYING BEHAVIOR PATTERN FOR TOYOTA MOTORS IN UAE", International Journal of Marketing & Financial Management, ISSN: 2348 –3954 (online) ISSN: 2349 –2546 (print), Volume 5,(Issue 4, Apr-2017), pp 01–21,*

A STUDY ON CONSUMER BUYING BEHAVIOR PATTERN FOR TOYOTA MOTORS IN UAE

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ABSTRACT

The automotive industry is facing new and pressing challenges. Globalization, individualization, digitalization and increasing competition are changing the face of the industry as we know it. In addition, increasing safety requirements and voluntary environmental commitments by the automotive industry will also contribute to the changes ahead. Size is no longer a guarantee of success. Only those companies that find new ways to create values will prosper in the future. The purpose of this paper is to present a short overview of the automotive industry today and highlight challenges facing the industry.

Key words: Automotive, Industry, TOYOTA, UAE

INTRODUCTION

Kiichiro Toyoda, founder of the Toyota Motor Corporation, was born in 1894. His father Sakichi Toyoda became famous as the inventor of the automatic loom. Inheriting the spirit of research and creation from his father, Kiichiro devoted his entire life to the manufacturing of cars, which was an unknown frontier at that time. After years of hard work, he finally succeeded in completing the A1 prototype vehicle in 1935. That was the beginning of the history of the Toyota Motor Corporation. In 2006, Toyota was engaged in a variety of projects designed to solidify its foundations while continuing to grow. On the product front, Lexus launched its new flagship model, the LS, and the new global Camry went on sale. In Japan, a new Corolla range was introduced, emphasizing the importance of this best-selling car. In manufacturing, several new projects were started around the world. In May, manufacture of the Camry began in Guangzhou, China, while in the United States, the Kentucky plant, which in October celebrated 20 years of production, started manufacturing the first Toyota hybrid vehicle to be made in North America, the Camry Hybrid. In November, the Texas plant began producing the new Tundra truck, a key vehicle in Toyota's North American lineup. In Japan, Toyota Motor Kyushu, Inc. began full-scale operations at its engine factory, while Toyota Motor Tohoku Co., Ltd. increased its manufacturing capacity.

In human resources development, following the establishment of the Asia Pacific Global Production Center in Thailand in August 2005, Toyota established the North American Production Center in the U.S. in February, and the European Global Production Center in the United Kingdom in March. Established as branches of the Global Production Center in Japan, these were created to spread Toyota's manufacturing knowledge and skills throughout the world in pace with the rapid growth of Toyota's overseas manufacturing. The centers educate trainers for local manufacturing plants in all regions, with trainees passing on what they learn to team members on their return to their plants.

In R&D, Toyota focused its efforts on three key areas: environment, safety and energy. It made a special effort in the area of the environment by expanding its lineup of hybrid vehicles, and has worked on R&D relating to plug-in hybrid. In addition, as part of Toyota’s efforts to respond to the diversification of energy, in 2007 Toyota plans to introduce a flex fuel vehicle* in the Brazilian market that will run on 100% bio-ethanol fuel. From this point on, based on the philosophy of providing “the right car, in the right place, at the right time,” and in accordance with the infrastructure and customer needs of each region, Toyota will continue to promote efforts to develop environmentally friendly technology and vehicles.

TOYOTA IN UAE

Toyota cars and 4x4 vehicles have constantly evolved over the years, and have quite rightly become benchmarks in their respective market segments, setting unrivalled standards in the automobile industry. A name that spells quality and value for money, Toyota enjoys a majority

Market share in the highly competitive and consumer conscious UAE market. Each one of its wide spectrum of vehicles is a leader in its class and the first choice of discerning consumers. With an exhaustive range of passenger cars that is designed to satisfy every customer and meet every possible budget, Toyota continues to dominate the UAE roads. Be it the revolutionary Echo, sporty xA, reliable Corolla, elegant Camry, the luxurious Avalon, the spacious Innova, the new Yaris Hatchback to the all new Yaris Sedan, each model is a winner in its class. No need to wonder, therefore, why every fourth passenger car in the UAE is a Toyota. For a country that offers a unique off-road experience, Toyota has an impressive line-up of 4 x4s. From the fun machine RAV4, to the affordable Prado, the mighty Land cruiser and the all new Fortuner, Toyota continues to lead the way. And that's not all. Toyota's unmatched range also includes light commercial vehicles such as the all New HILUX pickup cabs, vans like the HIACE, and passenger coaches like the COASTER. Toyota engineers have worked long and hard to make the year all models even better (a difficult job by any standards). It is this level of dedication that gives Toyota such a strong, competitive edge. A wide choice of models which meet every individual requirement, superior technological features and specifications, high quality, low overall cost of ownership and legendary resale value make every Toyota a sound investment.

MODELS OF TOYOTA IN UAE

Passenger Cars	4 Wheel Drives	Light Commercial Vehicle
Aurion V6	RAV4	Coaster
Avalon	FJ Cruiser	Hiace
Previa	Fortuner	Hilux
Innova	Land Cruiser Prado	
Yaris Sedan	Land Cruiser Station Wagon	
XA	Land Cruiser - Pick Up	
Yaris Hatchback		
Corolla		
Camry		

9. OBJECTIVES

To provide a scientific understanding of consumer buying behavior for automobiles specific with TMC (Toyota Motors Corporation). in UAE. With the aim of obtaining a clear-cut understanding of how people buy, what they buy, when they buy and why they buy.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Research Design :

As the topic is in the field of marketing and aims at identifying and describing dependent and independent variables of automobile buying behavior in UAE, the research design is descriptive in nature.

Population

The target population for the proposed research study comprises of existing and potential car owners in the UAE.

Sampling Design

Keeping in mind, the large population size, the researcher intends to identify and differentiate samples on the bases of age, brand, lifestyle, occupation etc; and categorize them as part of the representative sample to be tested upon. This design would ensure that the samples contribute meaningfully, both quantitatively and qualitatively.

Questionnaire Design

The questionnaire for the proposed research is self prepared. The questionnaire consists of two parts of questions the 1st part contain eight questions and 2nd part contain seventeen questions that would assess and analyze the factors associating/affecting automobile buying behavior for Toyota, such as:

- Customer needs
- Customer perceptions of current strategies
- Brand Image
- Lifestyle
- Psychographics

Data Collection

The primary data is collected with help of the auto-buyers scale from existing and potential car buyers from the emirates of Abu Dhabi, Dubai, Sharjah and Ajman.

The secondary data is collected from appropriate websites, journals and reference books pertaining to the topic of research

CONSUMER BUYING BEHAVIOR

Consumer behavior is the study of how people buy, what they buy, when they buy. It is a subcategory of marketing that blends elements from psychology, sociology, socio-psychology, anthropology and economics. It attempts to understand the buyer decision making process, both individually and in groups. It studies characteristics of individual consumers such as demographics, psychographics, and behavioral variables in

attempt to understand people's wants. It also tries to assess influences on the consumer from groups such as family, friends, reference groups, and society in general.

Introduction to Consumer Buying Behavior

The decision processes and acts of final household consumers associated with evaluating, buying, consuming, and discarding products for personal consumption. Consumers are constantly faced with the need to make the decisions about products. Some of these decisions are very important and entail great effort, whereas others are made on a virtually automatic basis.

Perspectives on decision making range from a focus on habits that people develop over time to novel situations involving a great deal of risk in which consumers must carefully collect and analyze information prior to making a choice. Many of our decisions are highly automated and made largely by habit. This trend is accelerating as marketers begin to introduce smart products that enable silent commerce where some purchases are made automatically by the products themselves (e.g., a malfunctioning appliance that contacts the repair man directly).

A typical decision process involves several steps. The first is problem recognition, in which the consumer first realizes that some action must be taken. This realization may be prompted in a variety of ways, ranging from the actual malfunction of a current purchase to a desire for new things based on exposure to different circumstances or advertising that provides a glimpse into what is needed to 'live the good life'.

Once a problem has been recognized and is seen as sufficiently important to warrant some action, information search begins. This search may range from simply scanning memory to determine what has been done to resolve the problem in the past to extensive fieldwork in which the consumer consults a variety of sources to amass as much information as possible. In many cases, people engage in surprisingly little search. Instead, rely on various mental shortcuts, such as brand names or price, or they may simply imitate others.

In the evaluation of alternatives stage, the product alternatives that are considered comprise the individual's evoked set. Members of the evoked set usually share some characteristics; they are categorized similarly. The way products are mentally grouped influences which alternatives will be considered, and some brands are more strongly associated with these category than others (i.e., they are more prototypical).

Consider the purchase of an automobile. You generally will not consider different options until some event triggers a need, such as a problem needing potentially expensive repair. Once this need has put you 'on the market', you begin to ask your friends for recommendations regarding dealerships and car models. After visiting several dealerships, you test drive several models and finally decide on a particular model. After the monthly payments, you begin to wonder if instead you have purchased a more expensive but potentially more reliable model. Over the next five years, the car has several unexpected breakdowns that lead you to want to purchase a different brand, but you have been very happy with the services of the local dealership and decide to again purchase your next car there.

In this particular case, the following *generic model of consumer decision making* appears to hold;

- ====> **need recognition**
- =====> **information search**
- =====> **Evaluation of alternatives**
- =====> **Purchase decision**
- =====> **Post purchase behavior**

DATA ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

1. Break up of age group

< 18	0%
18 - 25	36.92%
26 - 33	36.92%
34 - 42	20%
43 - above	6.16%

Break-up of Age

2. Break up of gender

Male	86.15%
Female	13.85%

3. Marital status

Divorced	0%
Married	58.46%
Single	41.54%

4. Break up of population

Asian	73.28%
Local	10.77%
Expat Arab	13.85%
Western	2.10%

5. Living duration in UAE

< - 10 Yrs.	32.50%
11 – 20 Yrs.	32.11%
21 – 30 Yrs.	32.31%
31 – above Yrs.	3.08%

6. Break up of job status

Student	9.23%
Administration	40%
Sales & Marketing	27.69%
Operational	16.92%
Others	6.16%

7. Break up of annual income (AED).

< 48,000	35.38%
48,000 – 60,000	32.31%
61,000 – 72,000	4.62%
73,000 – 84,000	7.69%
85,000 - above	20%

Annual Income (AED).

8. Who in house hold decides about buying a car?

My self	43.08%
Combine family	53.85%
Less role	3.08%

Who takes decision about buying a car?

9. Purpose of buying a car.

Personal use	33.85%
Family use	40%
Official use	0%
All these	26.15%

10. Prefer to buy a car.

New car	80%
Second hand car	9.23%
Doesn't matter	10.77%

11. Break up of car owners.

Chevrolet	1.54%	Mazda	1%
Ford	1%	Mitsubishi	3.08%
Toyota	47.77%	Nissan	3.08%
Hyundai	1.23%	Pevgeot	1.54%
Honda	9.23%	Other	14.38%
Kia	0.77%	None	15.38%

People have owned car

12. How long using own car.

< - 1 Year	21.54%
2 – 4 Yrs.	41.54%
5 - above	21.54%
None	15.38%

13. Buying a car again from the same brand.

Yes	67.69%
No	16.92%
None	15.38%

Buying again same Brand

14. Which brand comes to the mind first.

Chevrolet	4.62%	Mazda	1.54%
Ford	0%	Mitsubishi	0%
Toyota	69.23%	Nissan	0%
Hyundai	0%	Pevgeot	0%
Honda	10.77%	Other	13.85%
Kia	0%		

The Brand comes in mind first

15. The most important factor consider, to select a brand.

Experience	36.92%
All facilities under one roof	32.31%
Loyal with this brand	12.31%
Attractive deal	6.15%
Choice of different models	9.23%
Other	3.08%

Major Factor Consider to Buy a Car

Experience	All Facilities Under One Roof	Loyal With This Brand
Attractive Deal	Choice of Different Models	Other

16. Prefer to buy a car through.

Bank car financing	64.62%
Cash purchase	30.77%
Personal loan	4.62%

Buying a Car through

Bank Car Financing	Cash Purchase	Personal Loan
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17.Years Preferred for car financing.

< 3 yrs.	15.38%
3 – 4 yrs.	36.92%
5 yrs.	16.92%
None	30.77%

18. Prefer to buy a car.

With down-payment	35.38%
Without down-payment	33.85%
None	30.77%

19. Consider ease of parts availability In future.

Yes	96.92%
No	3.08%

20. If company is financing,

Then the brand would like to buy.

Toyota	52.31%	Infinity	1.54%
BMW	6.15%	Lexus	6.15%
Mercedez	9.23%	Range Rover	3.08%
Audi	3.08%	Chevrolet	1.54%
Honda	9.23%	Other	7.69%

Car Financing by company

■ Toyota	■ BMW	■ Mercedez	■ Audi	■ Honda	■ Infinity	■ Lexus	■ Rang Rover	■ Chevrolet	■ Other
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21. Prefer to buy a Toyota?

Yes	87.69%
No	12.31%

Prefer to buy a Toyota

Note:

Out of 100% sample size the consumer only wants to go for TOYOTA is 69.23%. This exercise of gauging subconscious opinion has proven successful, As the result differs only by 2% which is quite negligible according to the research standards if the population is 65.

22. Break up of age group Choosing TOYOTA.

< 18	0%
18 - 25	20%
26 - 33	24.62%
34 - 42	18.46%
43 - above	6.15%

Age Break-Up for Toyota Consumers

23. Break up of population for TOYOTA.

Asian	52.31%
Local	9.23%
Expat Arab	7.69%
Western	1.54%

24. Break up of annual income (AED),

For TOYOTA consumers.

< 48,000	26.15%
48,000 – 60,000	23.08%
61,000 – 72,000	4.62%
73,000 – 84,000	1.54%
85,000 - above	13.85%

25. Who in house hold decides

About buying a TOYOTA?

My self	26.15%
Combine family	40%
Less role	3.08%

Who Decide to Buy a Toyota?

26. Purpose of buying a TOYOTA.

Personal use	26.15%
Family use	27.69%
Official use	0%
All these	15.38%

Buying a Toyota for ?

27. Prefer to buy a car, TOYOTA.

New car	55.38%
Second hand car	9.23%
Doesn't matter	4.62%

Buying a Toyota ?

28. the most important factor consider to Select a TOYOTA.

Experience	26.15%
All facilities under one roof	23.08%
Loyal with this brand	10.77%
Attractive deal	0%
Choice of different models	7.69%
Other	1.54%

Most Important Reason to Select Toyota

29. Prefer to buy a car, TOYOTA Through.

Bank car financing	43.08%
Cash purchase	21.54%
Personal loan	4.62%

Influencing Factors

Preferences table in percentage to have TOYOTA.

a	Good look	51.11%
b	Mileage	28.89%
c	Safety	44.44%
d	Symbolic	11.11%
e	Speed	22.22%
f	Size	13.33%
g	Resale value	44.44%
h	Fuel consumption	42.22%
i	Luxury	13.33%
j	Reliability	26.67%
k	Economical maintenance	42.22%
l	Spare parts availability	44.44%
m	Reputed car manufacturer	15.56%
n	Has a wide model line up	2.22%
o	Good customer care for sale	8.89%
p	Good customer care for service	4.44%
q	Modern in tune with time	6.67%

Influencing Factors

Preferences table in percentage to buy a TOYOTA In the future .

a	Good look	55.56%
b	Mileage	26.67%
c	Safety	53.33%
d	Symbolic	8.89%
e	Speed	17.78%
f	Size	11.11%
g	Resale value	64.44%
h	Fuel consumption	53.33%
i	Luxury	28.89%
j	Reliability	28.89%
k	Economical maintenance	42.22%
l	Spare parts availability	57.78%
m	Reputed car manufacturer	20%
n	Has a wide model line up	8.89%
o	Good customer care for sale	6.67%
p	Good customer care for service	17.78%
q	Modern in tune with time	2.22%

Preferences table in percentage for the TOYOTA Comparing with other automotive brands.

1	Toyota	42.05%
2	Lexus	3.59%
3	BMW	3.59%
4	Mitsubishi	1.03%
5	Honda	16.41%
6	Mercedez	4.62%
7	Kia	0.51%
8	Audi	1.54%
9	Hummer	0.51%
10	Chevrolet	4.10%
11	Nissan	11.79%
12	Pevgeot	1.03%
13	Ford	2.56%
14	Mazda	0.51%
15	Volks Wagon	1.03%
16	Porche	1.03%
17	Dodge	1.03%
18	Others	2.55%

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Questionnaire

PART -A

- 1) Name:- _____
- 2) Age:-
 <18 18-25 26-33 34-42 43-above
- 3) Gender:-
 Male Female
- 4) Marital Status:-
 Single Married Divorced
- 5) Nationality:- _____
 Asian Expat Arab Local Western
- 6) How long living in U.A.E.
 < -10 yrs. 11-20 yrs. 21-30 yrs. 31-above (yrs.)
- 7) Occupation:- _____
(please specify your designation)
- 8) Annual Income (in AED):-
 Below 48,000 48,000-60,000 61,000-72,000
 73,000-84,000 85,000-above

Part –B

- 1) Can you please tell, who in your household decides about buying a car? (Single Response)
- All decisions are taken by myself only.
 All decisions are taken by jointly by me and my wife/other family members.
 I have limited/less role in the decision.
- 2) Will you buy a car for ?
- Personal Use For Family Use For Official Use For All These
- 3) Will you buy a ?
- New Car Second hand Car Doesn't matter
- 4) Which car do you own?
- Chevrolet Ford Toyota Hyundai Honda Kia
 Mazda Mitsubishi Nissan Pevgeot Other. None

5) Please specify the reason behind buying this car? (mark any five)

Rating from 1-5 (1 is for top priority & 5 for lowest)

- | | | |
|------------------------------------|---|---|
| <input type="checkbox"/> Good Look | <input type="checkbox"/> Resale Value | <input type="checkbox"/> Reputed Car Manufacturer |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Mileage | <input type="checkbox"/> Fuel Consumption | <input type="checkbox"/> Has a wide Model Lineup |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Safety | <input type="checkbox"/> Luxury | <input type="checkbox"/> Provide good customer care for sale |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Symbolic | <input type="checkbox"/> Reliability | <input type="checkbox"/> Provide good customer care for service |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Speed | <input type="checkbox"/> Economical to maintain | <input type="checkbox"/> Modern in tune with time |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Size | <input type="checkbox"/> Spare Parts Availability | <input type="checkbox"/> None |

6) How long you have been using this car?

- < - 1 year 2-4 yrs 5-above (yrs) None

7) Will you buy the car again from same Brand?

- Yes No None

Please specify reason:

8) Can you please tell, which three cars you will prefer to buy?

- a). _____
b). _____
c). _____

9) Please specify which Car Brand comes to your mind first.

- Chevrolet Ford Toyota Hyundai Honda Kia
 Mazda Mitsubishi Nissan Peugeot Other.

10) Factors consider to buy a car. (mark any five)

Rating from 1-5 (1 is for top priority & 5 for lowest)

- | | | |
|------------------------------------|---|---|
| <input type="checkbox"/> Good Look | <input type="checkbox"/> Resale Value | <input type="checkbox"/> Reputed Car Manufacturer |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Mileage | <input type="checkbox"/> Fuel Consumption | <input type="checkbox"/> Has a wide Model Lineup |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Safety | <input type="checkbox"/> Luxury | <input type="checkbox"/> Provide good customer care for sale |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Symbolic | <input type="checkbox"/> Reliability | <input type="checkbox"/> Provide good customer care for service |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Speed | <input type="checkbox"/> Economical to maintain | <input type="checkbox"/> Modern in tune with time |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Size | <input type="checkbox"/> Spare Parts Availability | |

11) What is the most important reason, why you choose this Brand.

- Experience Attractive Deal
 All facilities under one roof Choice of different Models
 Loyal with this Brand Other.

12) Would you prefer to buy this car through:

- Bank car financing scheme Personal Loan
 Cash purchase

13) How many years would you prefer for lease?

- < 3 yrs. 3-4 yrs. 5 yrs. None.

14) Would you prefer to buy this car:

- With down-payment Without down-payment None

15) Do you consider ease of parts availability when you buy a car?

- Yes No

16) If your company is financing for you, then which car (brand) would you like to buy?

(please specify the car)

17) Would you prefer to buy a TOYOTA?

- Yes No

(please specify reason)